

HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF CULTURAL HERITAGE CONSERVATION

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Abstract. Conservation is the process of preserving and managing changes in a cultural heritage site, maintaining its value and, if necessary, repairing it. Certain legal requirements apply to "retention". In the law, it is believed that this should be interpreted as "protection from harm" - it is protection from damage to its value, not just a material object. By object conservation, that is, absolute physical conservation can be approached, but such cases are extremely rare. Most of our heritage sites are capable of some degree of adaptation or recycling without losing their value. In fact, the change is often essential to facilitate the optimal use of the facility in order to continue receiving investment.

Key words: conservation, heritage, preservation, adaptation, architecture, fine and applied arts.

Abstrakt. Konservatsiya - madaniy meros ob'ektidagi o'zgarishlarni saqlash va boshqarish, uning qiymatini saqlab qolish va kerak bo'lganda uni ta'mirlash jarayoni. "Saqlash" uchun muayyan qonuniy talablar qo'llaniladi. Qonunda buni "zarardan himoya qilish" deb talqin qilish kerak, deb hisoblashadi - bu moddiy ob'ekt emas, balki uning qiymatiga zarar etkazishdan himoya qilishdir. Ob'ektni saqlash orqali, ya'ni mutlaq jismoniy saqlanishga yaqinlashish mumkin, ammo bunday holatlar juda kam uchraydi. Bizning meros ob'ektlarimizning aksariyati o'z qiymatini yo'qotmasdan, ma'lum darajada moslashish yoki qayta ishlashga qodir. Darhaqiqat, o'zgartirish ko'pincha investitsiyalarni olishni davom ettirish uchun ob'ektdan optimal foydalanishni osonlashtirish uchun zarurdir.

Kalit so'zlar: konservatsiya, meros, saqlash, moslashtirish, arxitektura, tasviriy va amaliy san'at.

Аннотация. Консервация — это процесс сохранения и управления изменениями объекта культурного наследия, поддержания его ценности и, при необходимости, его восстановления. К «охране» применяются определенные юридические требования. В законе считается, что это следует трактовать как «защиту от вреда» — это защита от повреждения его ценности, а не только материального объекта. К консервации объектов, то есть к абсолютной физической консервации, можно подойти, но такие случаи крайне редки. Большинство объектов нашего наследия можно в той или иной степени адаптировать или переработать без потери своей ценности. Фактически, изменения часто необходимы для обеспечения оптимального использования объекта и продолжения получения инвестиций.

Ключевые слова: консервация, наследие, сохранение, адаптация, архитектура, изобразительное и прикладное искусство.

Cultural heritage is a gift from our ancestors. As early as the time of Sopoltepa and Afrosiyob, humanity discovered drainage lines and urban planning. Because the evidence was hidden from people, we lost a lot of time trying to figure it out. Every effort should be made to ensure that they are preserved, repaired and used from time to time. Cultural heritage is not only

historical works of art and buildings, the city as a whole, neglected technical achievements, forgotten and cherished traditions.

Conservation is the process of preserving and managing changes in a cultural heritage site, maintaining its value and, if necessary, repairing it. Certain legal requirements apply to "retention". In the law, it is believed that this should be interpreted as "protection from harm" - it is protection from damage to its value, not just a material object. By object conservation, that is, absolute physical conservation can be approached, but such cases are extremely rare. Most of our heritage sites are capable of some degree of adaptation or recycling without losing their value. In fact, the change is often essential to facilitate the optimal use of the facility in order to continue receiving investment.

Heritage areas of different eras are like footprints and marks left by people hundreds of years ago. Missing such a sign can cause people to lose their way. It is what defines the people, their way of life and the culture of today. Among the historical remains of cultural heritage, the most important are architecture, fine and applied arts, as well as technologies and technical achievements. Most of the cultural heritage sites of cities or historic cities are suitable for flexible use and can contribute to the growth of the city's economy. They can be used to develop the tourism industry. At the same time, due to neglect, many historical structures of the city have lost their importance, attractiveness and ceased to be useful. Such structures must be restored and reused. Many buildings are designed to serve one purpose when constructed and can be adapted for another when the purpose is no longer meaningful.

Cultural heritage care has a centuries-old history and is primarily focused on the repair and maintenance of objects for their continued use and aesthetic enjoyment. Until the beginning of the 20th century, artists were usually involved in the repair of damaged works of art. However, in the 19th century, when scientists such as Michael Faraday began to study the harmful effects of the environment on works of art, the fields of science and art became increasingly intertwined. In addition, the researcher Louis Pasteur also conducted scientific analysis on the paint used in historical visual art works.

The first organized attempt to apply a theoretical framework to cultural heritage conservation occurred in Great Britain in 1877 with the founding of the Society for the Preservation of Ancient Buildings. William Morris and Philip Webb founded the society. They were deeply influenced by the studies of John Ruskin. In the same period, a French movement with similar goals developed under the leadership of Eugène Viollet-le-Duc, an architect and theoretician, famous for the renovation of medieval buildings.

The rules of preservation of cultural heritage as a separate field of research were originally developed in Germany. There, in 1888, Friedrich Rathgen Königlichen became the first chemist to work at the Berlin Royal Museum. He not only developed a scientific approach to the care of objects in collections, but also disseminated this approach in 1898 with the publication of the Guide to Heritage Conservation.

Early development of cultural heritage conservation in any region of the world is usually associated with the creation of positions for chemists in museums. In Great Britain, research into the conservation of fine art, ceramics and stonework has been carried out since 1900 by Arthur Pilans Laurie, an academic chemist and Chancellor of Heriot-Watt University. Laurie's interests were supported by William Holman Hunt. In 1924, chemist Harold Plenderlait began working at the British Museum with Dr. Alexander Scott in the newly formed Department of Scientific and Industrial Research, thereby establishing the profession of heritage conservation in Great Britain.

This section was created by the museum to address the deteriorating condition of the objects in the collection (damage to the collections caused by storage in the London Underground tunnels during the First World War). The establishment of this department shifted the focus on the development of heritage conservation theory and practice from Germany to Great Britain, and at the same time became a major force in this emerging field. In 1956, Plenderleith wrote an important handbook called "The Conservation of Antiquities and Works of Art". He set new standards for the development of the science of art and heritage protection.

The development of cultural heritage preservation in the United States can be traced to the work of the Fogg Art Museum and its director from 1909 to 1944, Edward Waldo Forbes. He encouraged technical research and was chairman from 1932 to 1942 of the advisory committee for the first technical journal. The manual "Technical studies in the field of Fine Arts" published by Fogg is also of great importance. Importantly, he included chemists among the museum staff. Rutherford John Gettens, one of the chemists, was the first in the United States to work permanently in an art museum. He worked with George L. Stout, the founder and first editor of Technical Studies. Began working with fine art materials at Oliver Brothers Art Restoration and Conservation - Boston, co-founded by Gettens and Stout. They invented the hot vacuum table in the 1920s to prime paintings. They received a patent for this table in 1937. The prototype table that Taylor designed and built himself is still in operation. Oliver Brothers is the first and longest continuously operating art restoration company in the United States.

Attention to the development of cultural heritage protection was then accelerated in Great Britain and America, and the first International Organizations for the Protection of Cultural Heritage appeared in Britain. The International Institute for the Conservation of Historic and Artistic Works (IIC) was established in 1950 under British legislation as "a permanent organization for the coordination and improvement of the knowledge, methods and standards of work necessary for the protection and conservation of valuable materials of all kinds". Historians and theorists such as Cesare Brandi have also played an important role in developing the scientific theory of cultural heritage protection. Ethical issues have been at the forefront of changes in the field of cultural heritage protection in recent years. The most important was the idea of preventive protection of cultural heritage. This concept was first developed in Harry Thomson's book on conservation work, *The Museum Environment*. Thomson's career was associated with the National Gallery in London. It was here that he established a series of guidelines and environmental controls for the best conditions under which objects could be stored and displayed in a museum environment. Although his specific guidelines are no longer strictly followed, they have inspired the field of cultural heritage conservation.

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